

THROUGH-WIDTH DELAMINATION IN NON-SYMMETRIC LAMINATE

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SUMMARY: This report outlines the preliminary results in through-width delamination specimens made of graphite/epoxy prepreg tape with graphite/epoxy prepreg cloth. The results obtained by MSC/NASTRAN in finite element model were in very good accordance when compared to classical theory, presented in ref. [1]. The specimen not only contains two types of graphite/epoxy, tape and cloth, but also presents a non-symmetrical laminate. Residual strength test after 60,000 cycles is showed.

KEYWORDS: Delamination, Non Symmetric Laminate, Residual Strength

INTRODUCTION

In aerospace designs, we know about the many possibilities of the use of composite material. We also know about its advantages, disadvantages, limitations and recommendations. However in the practical design, due to the production process and costs, sometimes the recommendations are not followed. For example is it possible to have a non-symmetrical laminates made of tapes as well as fabrics. Most of the composite material reports mention symmetrical laminates made of tapes [2], [3], [4]. Therefore, this report presents the delamination behavior of non-symmetrical laminates made of tapes as well as fabrics. Non linear analysis using MSC-Nastran finite element software [5], showed very good results and it is easy to use. Four different specimens with delamination length of 0, 10, 20 and 30 mm were tested. Residual strength after 60,000 cycles were compared.

SPECIMEN DEFINITION

Specimen definition is shown in figure 1 where 1 C, denotes one carbon/epoxy fabric ply and 1 T, denotes one carbon/epoxy tape ply, with the properties of the table 1.

Table 1 – Material Properties

Material	E_1	E_2	G_{12}	ν_{12}	t
	[GPa]	[GPa]	[MPa]		[mm]
Fabric	64.1	64.1	4.7	0.05	0.35
Tape	123.4	2.0	5.8	0.29	0.18

Four different specimens with delaminations length $2a$, equal to 0, 10, 20 and 30 mm were made. Twelve specimens were cycled in compression loading until 60,000 cycles with stress ratio, $R = 0.20$.

Fig. 1 - Specimen definition

FINITE ELEMENT ANALYSIS

Basically the finite element model is divided in four distinct regions as shown in the Figure 2. The finite element model used for MSC/NASTRAN analysis has 153 nodes and 128 four-node isoparametric elements (CQUAD4). In the regions A and B, MAT1 card (isotropic material property definition) was used with the engineering equivalent properties. In the regions C and D, MAT2 card (anisotropic material property definition) was used along with the coefficients of rigidity C_{ijkl} of the graphite/epoxy. The thickness “ t ” in the figure correspond to 1C 0,90° and 1C ±45° plies. Due to symmetry condition only half of model was necessary. The displacement along the line $x_1 = -a$ on direction x_1 is set to zero. At $x_1 = -a$ and $x_2 = H$, the displacement on direction x_2 is set to zero to prevent rigid body motion. At $x_1 = l$ and $x_2 = H$, the displacement on direction x_2 is set to zero. Due to different material properties, the SPCD card (defines an enforced displacement value) was used to applied a constant loading. Figure 3, shows a schematic view of boundary conditions and loading. Figure 4, shows the finite element model result.

Fig. 2 - Finite Element Model - Subregions Definition

Fig. 3 - Boundary Conditions and Loading

V1
L1500
C100

Output Set: Case 6 Time 3.
Deformed(1.01): Total Translation

Fig. 4 – Finite Element Model Result – $2a = 30$ mm.

RESULTS

According to the reference [6], the finite elements model results were very good when compared with the reference [1]. Following the same procedure and based on the results shown in figures 4, 5 and 6 it can be observed that the solution 106 (non linear static analysis) of MSC/NASTRAN, are very well in accordance with the classical theory presented in ref. [1], when the delamination length is 30 mm. This first analysis is very important to verify any anomalies in the finite element model and to indicate the limit of the classical theory to obtain the energy release rate in accordance the reference [7]. Furthermore is very easy to perform.

Fig. 4 - Specimen 2 Results

Fig. 5 - Specimen 3 Results

Fig. 6 - Specimen 4 Results

The residual strength test results of the specimens with delaminations were compared with the specimens without delamination and the results are shown in figure 7. Figure 8, shows the specimen with delamination length equal 30 mm, after the residual strength test.

Fig. 7 – Residual Strength Comparison

Fig. 8 – Specimen 4 Residual Strength Test

CONCLUSION

The use of the classical theory for the delamination displacement is very simple to apply. Using the classical theory, laminates with, tapes or fabrics, symmetrical or non-symmetrical with delamination in any layer, can be pre-analyzed easily. With this theory we can adjust the finite element model for the next phase: the energy release rate analysis and the stresses field in the delamination. About the residual test, the small variation in the residual strength of the specimen tested is probably due to the low level load applied. It would be interesting to increase the loading level to obtain more information. As the delamination depends on many factors, the challenge is to find reliable simple solutions.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The author thanks the contribution and the support of the EMBRAER people to accomplish this work.

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